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MESSAGE FROM THE PRESIDENT

Dear students,

I would like to congratulate the present committee (2021-22) of the Student's Geographical Association for their hard work and dedication to publish the 56th volume of the "OBSERVER", an annual journal with ISSN No. 2230-9535. With the regular contributions from faculty members, research scholars and students across national and international institutions, this journal has been the symbol of academic pride and excellence of this department since its inception by late Prof. S.P. Chatterjee. The Journal has emerged as a platform to focus on the development of geographical understanding and its implementation towards the real-world geographical problems.

I on behalf of the faculty members, non-teaching staff, Research scholars and students wish the Student's Geographical Association all success and once again congratulate all the contributors of this volume.

Dr. Debasis Ghosh

Associate Professor & Head, Department of Geography

President, The Student's Geographical Association

University of Calcutta

From The Desk of Secretary

The annual journal of the association “The observer”, Volume 56th is published on teacher’s day 5th of September and contains valuable writings of eminent geographers, professors, research scholars and the students of our department.

It would not be out of the place to mention that without the guidance and inspiration of our respected professors and seniors of the Department, the success of the journal would have been impossible.

We express our earnest gratitude to all the teaching and non-teaching staffs, advisors and the students of Geography Department for their cordial cooperation and continuous support.

Pallab Gayen
(General Secretary)

Sudipta Das
Chetana Roy
Simanta Koley
(Assistant General Secretary)

Note from the editors

Esteemed Readers,

It gives us great pleasure and honour to announce that Department of Geography will celebrate teacher's day on 5th of September, 2022 at Ballygunge Science College campus, University of Calcutta by the students' Geographical Association. On this auspicious occasion, we are delighted to publish the 56th volume of our annual journal "THE OBSERVER" (ISSN: 2230-9535).

In this regard, we would like to express our sincere appreciation to our respected professors for their tireless cooperation and helpful recommendations throughout the editing of these articles. They have always served as a source of inspiration for us.

We did our best to choose and publish papers from different dimensions of Geography exploring new horizons. Our goal of this journal is to encourage publication from research scholars, teachers and student of geography. Furthermore, we would like to mention that this journal serves as a common platform for students to encourage their writing skills and publish their research ideas. This journal was created by student for student, and where young and old hands meet in terms of knowledge and ideas. This year, we have tried to deliver you this journal in a much better way, but we humbly apologize for all our inadvertent shortcomings.

The note remains incomplete if we do not acknowledge the encouragement and wholehearted support from our fellow classmates, juniors, scholars, the office staffs and the librarians.

Thanking you,

Yours truly,
Pulak Barman
Saptadipa Ghosal
Soumita Ghosh
(Editors)

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ANALYSIS OF RAINFALL TRENDS & ITS SPATIO-TEMPORAL VARIABILITY IN PURULIA DISTRICT DURING 1980-2021

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Abstract: The study investigates rainfall trends and variability of seasonal and annual of 20 IMD stations of Puruliya based on monthly precipitation data for 42 years (1980 to 2021) collected from the Indian Meteorological Department at a grid size of 0.25 latitude × 0.25 longitude. To compare and illustrate temporal data, basic statistical analyses including mean, standard deviation, coefficient skewness (CS), coefficient of kurtosis (CK), Mann-Kendall test (MK), and Sen's slope (SS) for seasonal and yearly rainfall data were utilized. The analysis revealed that most of the stations of study areas are dominated by decreasing trends. In the Winter, Pre-Monsoon, and Monsoon seasons decreasing trends of rainfall increases from the Western parts to the Eastern parts. Whereas, in Post Monsoon season decreasing trend increase from the Eastern part to the Western part. Analysis of the rainfall trends of this area could assist us in understanding the temporal trend of the climatic pattern.

Keywords: Rainfall Trend, Mann-Kendall (M-K), Sen's slope estimator (SS), ITA, PCI, SI Indices

Introduction:

In today's world, climate change has a massive influence on rainfall as well as water supplies. Rainfall attributes such as distribution, amplitude, extremeness, seasonality, and concentration pattern were altered by global climate change but vary with temporal and regional variability (Feng et al., 2013; Trenberth et al., 2015). Rainfall is not only a hydro-meteorological variable, but it is also a key player in the biotic ecosystem. Among all climate characteristics, it has the greatest impact on agricultural productivity (Rahman et al., 2017). Although climate change is a worldwide phenomenon, its effects vary greatly from place to place (Trajkovic & Kolakovic, 2009). In order to identify climate change, water resource and agricultural planners must conduct trend analyses of climatic variables in the microregion. Climate change's effects on many environmental characteristics have been studied extensively in many parts of the world. However, most climate change research has focused solely on temperature and precipitation (Chinchorkar et al., 2021; Jangra & Singh, 2021; Kumar et al., 2021; Patil et al., 2013).

In recent research, the Mann-Kendall (M-K), Sen's slope estimator (SS), and simple linear regression analysis (LRA) are the most frequently applied trend detection techniques (Bari et al., 2016; Wang et al., 2016). (Şen, 2012a) introduced an innovative trend analysis (ITA) that enables graphical trend evaluation without making any assumptions about the time series data. The ITA was widely used in different parts of the world to detect trends in hydro-meteorological variables.

In this context, the goal of the current study is to investigate the characteristics of rainfall, including seasonality, precipitation concentration, trends, and ITA, at 20 meteorological stations (IMD) in the Purulia district. To accomplish this study, the rainfall seasonality index (SI) (Walsh & Lawler, 1981) precipitation concentration index (PCI) (Oliver, 1980), non-parametric MK test (Kendall, 1948; Mann, 1945), and innovative trend analysis (ITA) method (Şen, 2012a) were used. As a result, studying the variability of climatic indicators has become a topic of significance for environmental researchers to better understand the trend and pattern of climate change and the future climatic scenario. The goal of this study is to examine the variability of five meteorological indicators in Purulia District from 1980

to 2021. Similarly, the study's objectives are to analysed the temporal changes in monthly, seasonal, and annual weather parameters.

Study Area: The region under the investigation is a large portion of the Indian plateau. The study area Purulia District is situated in the Western Part of the West Bengal State and the Eastern part of the Chotanagpur Plateau with an area of 6,259 KM². Its spatial extent is between 22°06' to 23°50' North Latitude and 86°05' to 86°75' East Longitude. The climate regime of the study area is typically a Tropical Savanna Climate (Aw) (Köppen et al., 1884); the winter season is a rather mild and dry period, whereas the summer season is hot and rainy. Despite receiving 1288 mm of precipitation yearly in the study region, drainage is high and storage is low because to the undulating topography, and differences in soil depth and slope, and this frequently leads to droughts throughout the district. (Rudra, 2012).

The Southwest monsoon is the principal source of rainfall in the district. There is a range of 1100 to 1500 mm in the average yearly rainfall. During the monsoon season, there is a lot of relative humidity—between 75% and 85%. However, during the sweltering heat, it drops to 25% to 35%. The temperature ranges widely, from 7 degrees Celsius in the winter to 46.80 degrees Celsius in the summer. (Purulia, 2016) In the Purulia area, there are several rivers. Kangsabati, Kumari, Silabati (Silai), Dwarakeswar, Subarnarekha, and Damodar are the most significant among them. Despite the fact that the region is crossed by multiple rivers, the undulating landscape causes 50% of the water to run off. (Purulia, 2016)

Data and Methods: 20 meteorological stations' annual rainfall data from Purulia and its surrounding region between 1980 and 2021 were used in the current study. Yearly precipitation data for 42 years (1980 to 2021) were collected from Indian Meteorological Department. The data has been divided into two equal parts, from 1980 to 2000 and 2001 to 2021 for ITA. Using the non-parametric Mann-Kendall test and Sen's Slope estimator, these data were examined for trends.

We used daily rainfall data from 1980 to 2021 (42 years), which were produced by the Indian Meteorological Department using a 0.25 latitude by 0.25 longitude grid. Thiessen polygons method was used to calculate the area of influence for each rain gauge station then we examine 20 Stations in the study area. The gridded dataset for IMD was created utilizing quality-controlled rainfall data from a network of evenly spaced out more than 3000 rain gauge stations throughout India. The detailed information on data generation is explained by (Pai et al., 2014). We divided Purulia district into four meteorological seasons, there Winter season: December to February, the Pre-Monsoon season: March to May, the Monsoon season: June to September, and Post-Monsoon: October and November. To determine the district's overall seasonal and yearly rainfall, the monthly data from each station were further accumulated during the winter, pre-monsoon, monsoon, and post-monsoon seasons. Basic

Figure 2: Location map of the study area.

Statistical analysis including mean, standard deviation, coefficient skewness (CS), coefficient of kurtosis (CK), and Mann-Kendall test, Sen's slope for seasonal and annual rainfall data were used to compare and visualize time series data. Arc GIS 10.8, QGIS 3.16, and GraphPad Prism 9.0.0 software has been used for mapping and data analysis purposes, whereas, for interpolation purposes, the inverse distance weightage (IDW) method was selected. XLSTAT 2019 Excel plug-in was used for the M-K test and Sen's slope estimator. The following sections provide descriptions of the numerous techniques employed in this work.

Mann Kendall:

The non-parametric Mann-Kendall test is used for trend analysis. (Kendall, 1948; Mann, 1945). The Mann-Kendall test is the method that is most frequently used to identify trends in hydrometeorological time series data. (Das & Bhattacharya, 2018). The test statistics(S) of the series $x^1, x^2, x^3, \dots, x_n$ are calculated by using the following formula (Kendall, 1948; Mann, 1945)

$$S = \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \sum_{k=j+1}^n \text{sign}(y_k - y_j)$$

Here, n indicates the length of the dataset, and y_k and y_j denote data points of time k and j,

$$\begin{aligned} &= +1 \text{ if } y_k - y_j > 0 \\ \text{Sign}(x_j - x_k) &= 0 \text{ if } y_k - y_j = 0 \\ &= -1 \text{ if } y_k - y_j < 0 \end{aligned}$$

The variance of S, VAR(S), is calculated as:

$$\text{VAR}(S) = \frac{1}{18} \left\{ n(n-1)(2n+5) - \sum_{j=1}^g t_j(t_j-1)(2t_j+5) \right\}$$

Here, g represents the tied groups' number, and t_j shows the extent of jth tied number. A set of sample data with synonymous values is called the tied groups.

The time-series statistics(S) identified with Kendall's T (tau) which is given as follows:

$$\tau = \frac{S}{B}$$

Where,

$$B = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}n(n-1) - \frac{1}{2}\sum_{j=1}^g t_j(t_j-1)} \sqrt{\frac{1}{2}n(n-1)}$$

The estimation of S and VAR(S) is calculated to progress standardized test measurement Z as follows when $n > 10$ (Gilbert, 1987)

$$Z = \begin{cases} \frac{S-1}{\sqrt{\text{VAR}(S)}} & , \text{ if } S > 0 \\ 0 & , \text{ if } S = 0 \\ \frac{S+1}{\sqrt{\text{VAR}(S)}} & , \text{ if } S < 0 \end{cases}$$

The Z statistic often shows growing and declining trends in the time series as positive and negative values, respectively. The alternative hypothesis (H_z) and the null hypothesis (H_0), respectively, show that there are no trends in the chosen time series. (Pearson & Hartley, 1966).

Sen's Slope:

Sen's Slope estimation (Sen, 1968) is a non-parametric method for trend analysis of the Hydroclimatic Dataset (Pal et al., 2017). The Magnitude of the rainfall treasure was calculated by using Sen's Slope estimator (slope Q). The slope Q can be obtained from N pair of data as:

$$Q_i = \frac{x_k - x_j}{k - j}, i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N, k > j$$

Where x_k and x_j present values of data at k and j times, and Q is the median slope respectively.

Innovative trend Line:

The innovative trend analysis was first proposed by (Şen, 2012b). It can recognise different combinations of trends in various periods of series data by looking at the ITA graph, and it can detect both the monotonic trend and the sub-trend in the time series dataset. (Pour et al., 2020). It can also manage outliers and data with autocorrelation. The monthly rainfall of the original series (j) is first divided into two subseries with an equal number of observations in order to execute ITA. A Cartesian coordinate system is then used to plot each series against one another after being reorganised into ascending order (Girma et al., 2020), When the X axis represents the first half of the data and the Y axis represents the second half. A straight line is fitted to the scatter plot denoting "monotonic trend or no trend" in the third phase. The time series show an increasing trend if the scatter is concentrated above the 45° line (1:1), whereas a declining trend is seen if the scatter is concentrated below the 1:1 line. (Cui et al., 2017). There is no trend in the data set if the scatter points are concentrated along the trend line (Sen 2012). The slope of ITA(Şen, 2012b) is calculated from the following equation:

$$B = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \frac{10(x_j - x_k)}{\bar{x}}$$

Here B denotes the ITA slope, n means the extent of specific sub-series, x_j , and x_k denote the values of the consecutive sub-series, and \bar{x} represents the mean of the 1st sub-series (x_2).

The relevance of ITA is, however, estimated using the probability distribution function (PDF) (Das et al., 2021a). If a standard normal PDF's confidence interval has a mean of zero and the ITA slope's standard deviation (a) is significant at level a , then, the confidence limit of trend is:

$$CL_{(1-\alpha)} = 0 \pm S_{ITA} \sigma_s$$

The null hypothesis (no slope) is rejected when the evaluated slope of the trend of ITA (SITA) is shown to be larger than the critical value. But in this analysis, the 95% confidence level is taken into account. (Das et al., 2021b).

Precipitation concentration index

Using the precipitation concentration index, the amount of rain and its erosivity were estimated. (Michiels et al., 1992; Oliver, 1980); This is calculated using the formula below.:

$$PCI_{\text{annual}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^{12} R_i^2}{(\sum_{i=1}^{12} R_i)^2} \times 100$$

where PCI represents the precipitation concentration index, and R_i is the rainfall in a month i .

However, When PCI values are less than 10%, (Oliver, 1980) recommends that precipitation concentration is below or that precipitation dispersion be uniform. PCI values between 11 and 15% indicate a moderate precipitation concentration; PCI values between 16 and 20% indicate an erratic

precipitation distribution. PCI values of more than 20%, on the other hand, indicate high precipitation concentration or very uneven precipitation concentration.

Rainfall seasonality index:

The study's rainfall regimes were calculated using the SI (Walsh & Lawler, 1981) by the following formula:

$$SI = \frac{1}{R} \sum_{n=1}^{12} \left| X_n - \frac{R}{12} \right|$$

Here X_n signifies the total monthly precipitation, and R signifies the total annual precipitation.

The SI may theoretically range from zero (assuming the same amount of rain falls in every month) to 1.83. (if total rainfall occurs in 1 month).

Results and Discussion:

Preliminary analysis and Indices: The preliminary analysis was carried out to find the statistical parameters counting mean, standard deviation (SD), coefficient of skewness (CS), coefficient of kurtosis (CK), in seasonal and annual time series rainfall data of each station of Purulia during 1980 to 2021 are summarized in Table 2. The values of the mean and SD for the winter rainfall varies between 39.77 to 67.48 mm and 44.83 to 87.55 mm. In the pre-monsoon season, the values of mean and SD of rainfall varies from 98.34 to 208.21 mm and 46.05 to 79.23 mm, respectively. The mean rainfall of the monsoon season varied from 899.00 to 1246.11 mm with SD varying between 204.74 to 372.74 mm. In the post-monsoon season, mean rainfall varies from 75.95 to 119.27 mm and SD varies from 64.07 to 120.82 mm. The minimum mean annual rainfall (<1334 mm) is found in the western part of Purulia, on the other hand, the maximum mean annual rainfall (>1495 mm) is found in the eastern part of Purulia. We found that the mean annual rainfall increases from the western part to the eastern part of Purulia. During the last 42 years in various seasons (winter, pre-monsoon, monsoon, post-monsoon) amount of rainfall decreases in the western part of Purulia. In winter, pre-monsoon, monsoon, and post-monsoon season the skewness value varies from 1.61 to 3.29, -0.18 to 1.91, -0.31 to 1.05, and 0.80 to 2.06. The average skewness values of this season are 2.14, 0.69, 0.34, and 1.28. The skewness value of annual rainfall varies from -1.61 to 1.31 and the average skewness value is .13. A positive skewness value indicates the asymmetric distribution of data and lies to the right of the station. On the other hand, a negative skewness value indicates the symmetric distribution of data and lies to the left side of the station. In winter, pre-monsoon, monsoon, and post-monsoon season the kurtosis value varies from 2.34 to 14.13, -1.30 to 4.84, -0.69 to 3.37, and -0.39 to 4.43. The average kurtosis value for this season is 5.69, 0.70, 0.27, and 1.30. The kurtosis value of annual rainfall varies from -0.47 to 6.36 and the average kurtosis value is 0.66. While skewness focuses on the overall shape, kurtosis focuses on the tail shape. The kurtosis of normal Distribution is 3. There are three situations in kurtosis: Platykurtic (when kurtosis value < 3), Leptokurtic (when kurtosis value > 3), Mesokurtic (when kurtosis value = 3).

Figure 2: Spatial pattern of mean annual and seasonal rainfall over the Purulia district.

PCI and SI were used to measure the concentration and seasonality of rainfall for all of the stations, and the results are given in the Figure 3. The obtained results show that irregular precipitation concentrations dominate the studied region. Except for the North-Western upper part of the Purulia District, almost 96% of the stations indicated variable rainfall concentrations (PCI = 18-20) and were spread over the whole study area. The region with the highest PCI value (above 20.80) is found in the 2nd station and the lowest PCI value is observed in the 17th Number station of the Study area. In the rest of the region, index values vary from 17.5-to 19.5. The SI data showed that the most of the study area's stations (almost 98%) were characterized by Equable but with a definite wetter season (SI = 0.20–0.39), mostly higher SI values located in an outer boundary region of the study area.

Figure 3: Spatial distribution of annual rainfall (a. Long-term average, b. CV in %, c. PCI, and d. SI)

Station Id	G1	G2	G3	G4	G5	G6	G7	G8	G9	G10	G11	G12	G13	G14	G15	G16	G17	G18	G19	G20
Latitude	85.8	85.75	86	86	86	86.3	86.25	86.25	86.5	86.5	86.5	86.5	86.5	86.75	86.8	86.8	86.75	86.5	87	87
Longitude	23.3	23.5	23	23.25	23.5	23	23.25	23.5	22.75	23	23.25	23.5	23.75	22.75	23	23.3	23.5	23.75	23.5	23.75
CV (%)	19.4	25.3	19.9	19.6	23.9	18.3	16.9	18.8	17.7	19.2	18.4	19.6	22.2	15.6	19.4	26.9	18.0	20.7	22.9	19.0
SI	20.2	20.8	19.9	19.6	20.4	19.5	19.4	20.2	18.8	18.5	18.7	19.9	20.2	17.8	18.2	18.8	18.9	20.2	18.6	19.1
PCI	0.215	0.224	0.222	0.209	0.216	0.216	0.210	0.216	0.217	0.213	0.211	0.217	0.214	0.215	0.210	0.214	0.214	0.218	0.213	0.210

Table 1: Vales of the coefficient of variation (%), seasonality index (SI) and Precipitation concentration index (PCI)

Figure 4: Temporal Variation of a. Winter, b. pre-Monsoon, c. Monsoon, d. post-Monsoon

Trend of Rainfall Using ITA: The innovative trend analysis was first proposed by Şen, (2012b). It can recognise different combinations of trends in different periods of time series data by looking at the ITA graph, and it can detect both the monotonic trend and the sub-trend in the time series dataset (Pour et al., 2020). The result of ITA detects the significant trends in each station. Our analysis exposed important trends in annual rainfall in each station of Purulia from the period 1980 to 2021. The decreasing trends were dominated in every station. In 3 stations (G17, G18, G19) out of two stations, we found that there were slightly dominated by increasing trends.

Figure 5: Plot of innovative trends of annual rainfall for the time period of 1980–2000 (first half) and 2001–2021 (second half)

Station	Winter			Pre-Monsoon			Monsoon			Post-Monsoon			Annual							
	Mean	SD	Skewness	Mean	SD	Skewness	Mean	SD	Skewness	Mean	SD	Skewness	Mean	SD	Skewness					
G1	40	45	4.84	2.13	100	68	4.84	1.91	903	205	0.18	0.31	80	68	2.29	1.48	1122	220	-0.27	0.07
G2	41	46	3.22	1.80	98	69	3.03	1.54	899	270	0.49	0.61	76	69	3.44	1.73	1115	286	-0.20	0.19
G3	50	50	2.52	1.64	134	79	1.09	1.10	1068	257	0.37	0.04	83	64	0.36	1.06	1336	269	0.82	-0.42
G4	45	48	3.20	1.76	129	64	0.25	0.62	1044	244	-0.45	-0.31	107	86	0.15	1.01	1325	263	-0.17	-0.54
G5	42	48	3.67	1.90	109	60	0.88	0.97	1037	291	3.37	1.01	99	82	-0.19	0.87	1287	312	1.47	0.55
G6	50	51	2.34	1.61	136	63	-0.20	0.59	1063	240	0.83	0.06	94	75	2.18	1.52	1343	248	1.13	-0.38
G7	49	52	4.55	1.96	141	61	0.21	0.68	1091	218	-0.46	-0.02	109	85	-0.06	0.98	1391	238	-0.09	-0.25
G8	46	52	5.45	2.12	124	51	-0.28	0.45	1095	253	0.02	0.57	105	83	-0.39	0.80	1369	261	0.94	0.55
G9	45	50	2.74	1.79	163	71	0.00	0.63	1113	221	0.85	0.00	118	121	4.01	2.06	1398	336	6.36	-1.61
G10	57	66	6.23	2.27	155	59	-0.16	0.27	1113	245	-0.07	-0.05	112	101	4.43	1.96	1437	280	-0.32	-0.20
G11	61	69	6.68	2.30	166	55	0.23	0.08	1183	260	-0.54	0.22	113	88	0.53	1.15	1523	284	-0.47	0.17
G12	46	52	5.12	2.05	127	46	-1.00	-0.18	1125	269	0.59	0.82	104	81	-0.08	0.91	1401	278	1.10	0.79
G13	43	49	6.44	2.27	121	58	-0.08	0.62	1100	269	-0.69	0.35	107	86	0.29	1.01	1371	308	-0.17	0.46
G14	53	52	3.01	1.62	208	77	2.30	0.81	1174	221	0.07	-0.28	119	101	2.70	1.67	1554	245	-0.04	-0.03
G15	60	70	8.70	2.62	185	61	0.18	0.71	1176	258	-0.24	0.26	119	94	1.24	1.34	1540	302	0.10	0.41
G16	67	88	14.13	3.29	188	67	0.61	0.75	1246	373	1.27	1.05	119	100	2.03	1.44	1620	441	1.73	1.31
G17	51	54	5.39	2.09	159	48	-0.87	0.02	1133	244	0.48	0.61	112	92	1.11	1.29	1455	265	1.38	0.67
G18	44	49	7.49	2.34	137	55	-1.30	0.07	1129	272	-0.12	0.48	116	97	-0.27	0.91	1425	298	0.43	0.44
G19	46	53	7.94	2.42	172	75	2.57	1.14	1036	272	0.03	0.54	111	94	1.93	1.42	1365	316	-0.19	0.20
G20	44	48	10.20	2.81	162	64	1.81	0.94	1126	269	-0.63	0.44	118	92	0.33	0.99	1449	279	-0.37	0.23
Average	49	55	5.69	2.14	146	63	0.70	0.69	1093	257	0.27	0.34	106	88	1.30	1.28	1391	286	0.66	0.13

Table 2: Statistical summary of annual and seasonal rainfall for studied station in Purulia District.

Trend of Annual rainfall:

The annual rainfall trend was detected by the Mann-Kendall test and Sen's slope test. We calculated Mann-Kendall and Sen's slope value of annual rainfall based on a rain gauge station, situated in Purulia and its surrounding area. Most of the stations were dominated by decreasing trends at α 0.05. On the other hand, 5 stations (G3, G9, G17, G18, G19) are dominated by an increasing trend at a p-value $>$ 0.05. The increasing trends are mainly observed in the Eastern and North-Eastern part of Purulia. Significantly, the G3 station in the western part shows an increasing rainfall trend at $p >$ 0.05. Whereas, decreasing trends are mostly found in the Western, Northern, Southern, North-Eastern, and Middle parts of the study area. Almost 80% of the station shows decreasing trends, whereas 20% of the station shows an increasing trend. According to the Mann-Kendall value the most increasing trend was found in the G19 station in the North-Eastern part with the value of +0.071 at p (0.522) $>$ 0.05. According to Sen's Slope value the most increasing trend was found in the G18 station in the North-Eastern part with the value of +2.294 at p (0.598) $>$ 0.05. According to the Mann-Kendall value and Sen's Slope value the far most decreasing trend was found in the G2 station in the far most western part with the value of -0.324 p (0.003) $<$ 0.05 and -10.263 p (0.003) $<$ 0.05.

Table 3: Table 3: M-K test and Sen's slope estimate result for rainfall in Seasonal time series (1981–2021)

Station Id	Winter		Pre-Monsoon		Monsoon		Post-Monsoon		Annual	
	Kendall's tau	Sen's slope								
G1	-0.129	-0.588	-0.141	-0.977	0.071	2.351	-0.059	-0.436	-0.115	-3.164
G2	-0.205	-0.750	0.027	0.204	0.264	6.649	0.243	7.559	-0.324	-10.263
G3	-0.179	-0.669	-0.192	-1.768	-0.001	-0.079	-0.120	-0.587	0.007	0.432
G4	-0.233	-0.846	-0.038	-0.345	0.085	3.579	-0.055	-0.470	-0.180	-6.030
G5	-0.128	-0.463	-0.080	-0.464	0.152	4.134	-0.050	-0.355	-0.188	-6.427
G6	-0.129	-0.588	-0.141	-0.977	0.071	2.351	-0.059	-0.436	-0.083	-2.333
G7	-0.184	-0.796	-0.127	-0.924	0.064	2.453	-0.022	-0.206	-0.156	-3.327
G8	-0.240	-1.026	-0.015	-0.151	0.148	4.168	-0.003	-0.010	-0.251	-6.711
G9	-0.038	-0.138	-0.245	-1.985	-0.003	-0.193	-0.103	-0.664	0.046	1.672
G10	-0.109	-0.546	-0.273	-2.174	0.148	4.215	-0.069	-0.395	-0.161	-6.431
G11	-0.200	-1.012	-0.166	-1.369	0.092	3.554	0.045	0.401	-0.154	-5.316
G12	-0.247	-0.854	-0.152	-0.918	0.029	1.267	0.029	0.206	-0.151	-4.131
G13	-0.192	-0.707	-0.153	-1.279	-0.063	-2.121	0.030	0.125	-0.013	-0.579
G14	-0.180	-0.847	-0.041	-0.302	0.041	1.147	0.064	0.723	-0.263	-7.453
G15	-0.165	-0.790	-0.108	-1.009	-0.008	-0.150	0.050	0.408	-0.098	-3.576
G16	-0.188	-1.047	-0.136	-1.468	-0.050	-2.874	0.122	1.308	-0.051	-1.817
G17	-0.183	-0.752	-0.137	-0.940	-0.123	-3.435	0.019	0.165	0.018	0.558
G18	-0.135	-0.556	-0.129	-0.821	-0.115	-4.246	-0.001	-0.041	0.059	2.294
G19	-0.153	-0.568	-0.150	-1.296	-0.115	-3.275	0.031	0.152	0.071	1.793
G20	-0.141	-0.382	-0.147	-1.112	-0.035	-1.044	0.121	0.858	-0.016	-0.151

Note: There were 95 % confidence level and 5 % significance level ($\alpha=0.05$)

Trend of Seasonal Rainfall:

Winter: The rainfall trend in the winter season was detected by Mann-Kendall and Sen's Slope value. The MK and SS values revealed decreasing magnitudes of the rainfall trend all over the study area at a 5% level. In Purulia, rainfall trends decrease continuously from year to year. According to the Mann-Kendall value the most decreasing test was found in the G12 station in the Northern part of the Purulia with the value of -247 at $p(0.022) < 0.05$, whereas the G16 station in the Eastern part of the Purulia was found to most decreasing trend according to Sen's Slope value of -1.047 at $p(0.081) > 0.05$. The most decreasing trend of rainfall is found in the Northern, North-Eastern, and Eastern parts of Purulia. Whereas, slightly decreasing trends were identified in the Western, South-Western part of Purulia at a 5 % level.

Pre-Monsoon: Magnitude of rainfall trends in pre-monsoon season detected by the Mann-Kendall and Sen's Slope value. The MK and SS value revealed that 95% of stations were dominated by decreasing rainfall trends and only 5% of stations were dominated by increasing rainfall trends at a 5 % level of significance. According to Mann-Kendall and Sen's Slope value, the far most decreasing trends were found in the G10 station in the Southern part, with the value -0.273 at $p(0.011) < 0.05$ and -2.174 at $p(0.011) < 0.05$. Only G2 station dominated by increasing rainfall trends with KM value 0.027 at $p(0.812) > 0.05$ and SS value 0.204 at $p(0.204) > 0.05$. The decreasing trends of rainfall in the Pre-Monsoon season are increasing from western parts towards the Eastern parts of the study area.

Monsoon: In this season south-western monsoon comes from the Bay of Bengal and the Indian Ocean towards North East. Most of the rainfall occurs in this season over the Indian Subcontinent. In this study area, 55 % of stations were dominated by increasing rainfall trends and 45 % of stations were dominated by decreasing rainfall trends at a 5 % significance level. According to Mann-Kendall and Sen's Slope value, the most increasing trends were found in the G2 station in the Western parts, with Mk value 0.264 at $p(0.014) < 0.05$ and SS value 6.649 at $p(0.014) < 0.05$. Whereas, most decreasing rainfall trends found in G17 station with MK value -0.123 at $p(0.255) > 0.05$ and G18 station with SS value -4.246 at $p(0.288) > 0.05$. Decreased trends of rainfall increase towards the Eastern part of the study area, whereas most rainfall occurs in the Eastern parts of the study area.

Post Monsoon: This season is called monsoon retreating season. Monsoon wind blows from North-East towards South-West. In this study area, 50 % of stations were dominated by increasing rainfall trends and 50 % of stations were dominated by decreasing rainfall trends at a 5 % significance level. Most of the stations that are located in the Eastern and North-Eastern portions of the study areas were dominated by increasing rainfall trends, but the most increasing trends are found in the G2 station with Mk value 0.243 at $p(0.024) < 0.05$ and SS value 7.559 at $p(0.024) < 0.05$ in the western portion of the study area. The most decreasing trends were found in G3 station with Mk value -0.12 at $p(0.269) > 0.05$ and SS value -0.587 at $p(0.269) > 0.05$. Significantly in this season rainfall trends increase from Western parts to Eastern parts of the study area.

Figure 6: Spatial variation of Mk tau and Sen's Slope for annual and seasonal rainfall

Conclusion:

The study area Purulia is positioned in the Western part of West Bengal and the Eastern part of the Chotanagpur plateau region. In this study, we examine the trends of seasonal and annual time series data for 42 years (1980-2021) for 20 IMD stations of Purulia. Elementary Statistical analysis contains mean, standard deviation, coefficient skewness (CS), coefficient of kurtosis (CK), ITA, PCI, SI, Mann-Kendall test (MK), and Sen's slope (SS) for seasonal and annual rainfall data were used to compare and visualize time series data. The present study revealed that there occur substantial fluctuations in seasonal and annual rainfall in Purulia during the last 42 years. The analysis exposed that most of the stations of study areas are conquered by declining trends. In the Winter, Pre-Monsoon, and Monsoon

seasons declining trends of rainfall rise from the Western parts toward the Eastern parts. The district experiences relatively variable rainfall, with the highest concentration of rainfall occurring during the monsoon season. Although, during Post Monsoon season declining trend rises from the Eastern part to the Western parts. The Eastern and North-Eastern have the highest annual rainfall but in this region, declining trends arise in the highest amount. The Western part has the lowest annual rainfall but, in this region, declining trends arise in the lowest amount. The People in this area are experiencing water shortages owing to a lack of rainfall; this phenomenon is affecting this drought-prone zone of the state. Also, Purulia District has experienced severe drought multiple times in the last decade. Investigation of the rainfall trends of this area, Total and mean rainfall has fluctuated well for that significant water shortage at the surface and subsurface levels. This rainfall analysis along with the map might also be very helpful for agricultural development and stockholders.

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GIS BASED URBAN FLOOD VULNERABILITY ASSESSMENT IN EASTERN INDIA -A CASE OF BHUBANESWAR CITY, ODISHA

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***Abstract-** Bhubaneswar, being a planned city in Eastern India has been facing the problem of water logging for a decade in several areas. The study focused on mapping flood vulnerable zones of Bhubaneswar based on ALOS PALSAR DEM. Using “AHP and GIS techniques”. Some natural factors causing flood are taken such as rainfall, drainage density, slope, soil and land use. Weights were assigned to each factor using “AHP” technique. The approach resulted in “Urban Flood Vulnerability Zone map” and classified into five zone e.g., very low, low, moderate, high and very high. Mitigation measures are recommended for the identified flood risk areas in Bhubaneswar.*

Key words: Urban Flooding, Vulnerability, GIS. Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP,), Mitigation

Introduction

“Urban flooding” or pluvial flooding causes the land or property inundation within a built environment, prone to densely populated areas. Basically, it is caused by heavy rainfall, overwhelming drainage capacity and has huge adverse economic and social impacts. These problems in city area are gradually increasing if changes are not made to the haphazard development of buildings, infrastructures and poor urban drainage management and leads to great obstructions of daily life drains by demarcating flow routes of natural drainage and their sub-catchments from “ASTER DEM”. Yashon O. Ouma et al. (2014) mapped flood prone areas of the Eldoret Municipality in Kenya. The study integrated “Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP)” and “Geographic Information System (GIS)” analysis techniques to estimate the magnitude of flood risk areas, followed by a multi-parametric approach in the city. The study of urban flooding requires identification of flood prone areas and also the factors affecting it mostly.

Catherin R Sebastian et al. (2016) determined flood prone areas of urban area of Thiruvananthapuram (Trivandrum), Kerala State, India by creating a flood hazard map in a Geographic Information System (GIS) platform. And also determined the optimal positions of storm water and included some flood causing factors for the flood vulnerability mapping.

Bhubaneswar, the Capital City of Odisha now-a-days is facing the problem of water logging. Several areas and major roads remained water-logged for hours while flash flood conditions caused a number of vehicles to be struck in water. Urban flood hazard has significant threat to many cities worldwide especially on developing countries. The condition of sewerage and drainage network is poor and unspecified. Hence cannot cope with the volume of water, mostly blocked by rubbish and non-biodegradable garbage's. Illegal connections cause overflow of sewers, which is also unable to cope with the increased volumes. The flood ways are obstructed due to messy developments by encroaching floodplains reduces natural flood storage. Currently, increasing rate of impermeable surface in urban areas such as roads, roofs and paving means more run-offs. Precipitation follows quick reduction of the time to peak and produces higher peak flow in the drainage channels.

The city of Bhubaneswar has 10 major or primary drains and several secondary and tertiary drains flowing adjacent to the roads, flood plains, open areas and nearby areas have been recently developed into built areas- few converted to residential areas, others are encroached by city dwellers. The areas